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Report on the Release of Case Studies

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Deliverable Abstract

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project started in June 2022 and delivers nine new EOSC-Core components in support of a FAIR research life cycle, bridging the gaps identified in the EOSC SRIA. Five user-centric Case Studies have been designed to help drive the development and testing of these components and showcase the added values for the respective communities. This deliverable reports on the integration efforts undertaken in each of the Case Studies. It provides a detailed account of the specific integration outcomes, set within the context of the unique challenges and objectives of their respective communities, and offers a summary of the benefits gained through these integrations, accompanied by a set of recommendations for each of the integrated components.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
EOSC	The European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
CLIMATE	The Climate Case Study.
SPRDM	The EOSC Service Providers RDM Communities Case Study.
EINS	The European Integration of National-Level Services Case Study.
MATH	The Mathematics Case Study.
SSH	The Social Sciences & Humanities Case Study.
EOSC	The European Open Science Cloud
RDGraph	The EOSC Research Discovery Graph Service (RDGraph) delivers advanced discovery tools across EOSC resources and communities.
PIDGraph	The EOSC PID Graph offers a service to explore the DOIs and metadata from the DataCite data file through an API and regular data dumps.
MSCR	The Metadata Schema Crosswalk Registry allows registered users and communities to search, create, register and version schemas and crosswalks with PIDs.
DTR	The EOSC Data Type Registry allows the registration of many different data types.

PIDMR	The PID Meta Resolver offers a uniform interface that allows PIDs from different systems to be resolved and can simplify various processes.
CAT	Compliance Assessment Toolkit, a service being developed in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project to assist with EOSC PID Policy compliance assessment
RAiD	The RAiD service provides persistent, unique and resolvable information for research projects.
RSAC	The Research Software APIs and Connectors ensure the long-term preservation of research software in different disciplines
SWHM	The EOSC Software Heritage Mirror is a copy of the Software Heritage universal source code archive, operated in agreement with, but independently from the Software Heritage organization.
B2SHARE	B2SHARE is an EUDAT service to store and publish research data
B2FIND	B2FIND is EUDAT's metadata discovery portal
PID	Persistent Identifier: generally expected to be unique, resolvable, and persistent, but other features and performance aspects may apply.
DOI	A Digital Object Identifier is a persistent identifier or handle used to uniquely identify various objects
ORCID	An Open Researcher and Contributor ID is a name-independent person-identifier
ROR	ROR is a global, community-led registry of open persistent identifiers for research organizations
RDM	Research Data Management
ENES	The European Network for Earth System Modelling
CMIP	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project: a project of the World Climate Research Programme (WCRP) providing climate projections to understand past, present and future climate changes
VCR	The Virtual Collection Registry is a service to manage virtual collections
DOG	The Digital Object Gateway is a service that offers a uniform API to CLARIN services across various PID and repository systems.
Switchboard	The Switchboard is a service brokering between objects and tools that can operate on those objects.
CodeMeta	The CodeMeta Project is a rapidly growing movement to improve preservation, discovery, reuse and attribution of academic software.
CRIS	A Current Research Information System is a database or other information system to store, manage and exchange contextual metadata for the research activity funded by a research funder or conducted at a research-performing organisation.
CERIF	The Common European Research Information Format.

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Executive Summary

Within the FAIRCORE4EOSC project several components have been developed to address gaps identified in the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda. In order to help drive the development and testing of the project components, five user-centric Case Studies have been designed, representing 5 different communities, to integrate components in their workflow and showcase the added value for the respective communities. All the Case Studies exhibit similar challenges that exist among various stakeholder groups. Specifically: (i) research communities at both the European and national levels own datasets that are not yet accessible within the EOSC; (ii) while they utilize Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), they lack Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for different levels of data aggregation; and (iii) they rely on community-specific services for metadata management, which complicates cross-disciplinary reuse and interoperability.

This deliverable presents a report on the integration efforts undertaken in each of the Case Studies. Each Case Study provides a detailed account of the specific integration outcomes, set within the context of the unique challenges and objectives of their respective community, and concludes with a brief outlook. The report ends with a summary of the benefits gained through these integrations, alongside a set of recommendations for each of the components.

1 Introduction

FAIRCORE4EOSC, funded from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, is a project contributing to the Co-programmed European Partnership on the European Open Science Cloud. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a flagship EU initiative to deepen Open Science practices across the European Research Area (ERA). As such it contributes to several actions of the ERA policy agenda. EOSC is also recognised in the European strategy for data as the data space for science, research and innovation which shall be fully articulated with the other sectoral data spaces defined in the strategy.

The research and innovation action (RIA) FAIRCORE4EOSC develops nine new EOSC-Core components in order to support a FAIR EOSC and to enhance interoperability and discoverability of research outputs. Development activities of the components (WP2-6) are carried out by utilising existing services and technologies, as far as possible. To ensure that testing and development of components are driven by the needs of users, the project has identified five user-centric case studies (WP7). The case studies also act as early adopters of the components in the communities they represent.

Recent EOSC developments have complicated achieving project aims regarding the integration of the new FAIRCORE4EOSC components within the EOSC-Core. Due to the EOSC Federation and Node concept, introduced by the EOSC Procurement, the concepts of the Minimum Viable EOSC (MVE), the EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange and Federated Data as described in the FAIR lady report from the Sustainability Working Group and used in the FAIRCORE4EOSC proposal and project, became unclear and are still subject to change. The proposal and the Description of Action part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Grant Agreement acknowledged that FAIRCORE4EOSC largely relies on the results of EOSC Future and could potentially be affected in an unfavourable way by the decisions taken by the EOSC Partnership and other actors.

Even though the context for the services has changed considerably, the primary FAIRCORE4EOSC outputs to support a FAIR EOSC are in the process of being released to the public (March 2025). Though many EOSC integrations have been tested, the current EOSC architecture does not support releasing integrations of the services as envisioned. These services concretely contribute to improving the discoverability and interoperability of a continuously increasing amount of research outputs, even with a looser EOSC coupling. They are agnostic in discipline or geography and general in nature - and will surely gain further adoption both within and beyond EOSC.

Various stakeholder groups have a set of common challenges. The Case Studies help reveal these common challenges. Specifically: (i) research communities at both the European and national levels manage datasets that are not yet accessible within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC); (ii) although they employ Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), they lack Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for different levels of data aggregation; and (iii) they depend on community-specific services for metadata management, which poses challenges for cross-disciplinary data reuse and interoperability.

The five FAIRCORE4EOSC Case Studies are: (1) Climate, (2) EOSC Service Providers RDM Communities (SPRDM), (3) European Integration of National-Level Services (EINS), (4) Mathematics (MATH) and (5) Social Sciences & Humanities (SSH). The initial integration of the Case Studies with the beta releases of the components was completed in month 22 (M22) and documented in Deliverable D1.4, FAIRCORE4EOSC Cross-integration Beta Release Report¹. Currently, at month 34 (M34), the components have been released into production. Each of the five Case Studies has successfully completed the integration of multiple components, as presented in Table 1. Only one planned integration was not implemented: the EINS integration with the SWHM component; details are provided in Section 2.4.2.

¹ Zamani, T., & Koumantaros, K. (2024). D1.4 FAIRCORE4EOSC Cross-integration Beta Release Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12623667>

Case Study	Climate Change	EOSC Service Providers RDM Communities	European Integration of National-Level Services	Mathematics	Social Sciences & Humanities
Component					
RDGraph	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated
PIDGraph	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated
MSCR	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated
DTR	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated
PIDMR				Integrated	Integrated
CAT		Integrated			
RAiD	Integrated	Integrated	Integrated		
RSAC				Integrated	
SWHM			Not Integrated		

Table 1: EOSC-Core Components deployed in the FAIRCORE4EOSC Case Studies

This document presents a comprehensive report on the integration efforts undertaken within each Case Study. Each Case Study provides a detailed account of the tangible integration outcomes, contextualized within the specific challenges and objectives of their respective communities, along with a forward-looking perspective. The report concludes with a summary of the overall added value generated and a set of recommendations for each of the components.

2 Case Study Integration Report

This chapter will report on the final integration outcomes and the developments since the BETA release. Each Case Study will reflect on the usability of the components in the context of the concrete issues the Case Study defined at the start of the project and provide a brief outlook.

2.1 Climate Change

2.1.1 Case Study Integration Report

Climate modelers, facing the challenges posed by climate change, have a critical need for services that enhance the discoverability and reusability of research results. As part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, an investigation was conducted to explore how the new FAIRCORE4EOSC components could benefit the Climate Community. The IS-ENES (Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modeling)² infrastructure was selected as a test environment due to its broad range of climate research data from national and international projects associated with different funding streams. Two user portals, Climate for Impact³ and the Copernicus Climate Data Store⁴, are available, each with its own access client and a provenance plugin. The data within IS-ENES are extensive, and a typical use case considered is the creation of downstream data products. In this context, provenance information about the used data plays a crucial role to understand where the data originated from, how data has been processed, or even reprocessed. Additionally, the project context, involved institutions and individuals, related publications, and connections between the data are also of great importance.

In practice, however, data creation and reuse are typically separated, meaning the different stakeholders are uninformed of each other's work. Therefore, it is vital that users understand, through provenance data, how the data was created and which processes it has undergone. The IS-ENES infrastructure already provides many of these insights, but there is still room for improvement, particularly in the areas of project linkage and data connections. Currently, users often need to actively gather the relevant project data themselves, which can be time-consuming and cumbersome.

Another key aspect is the automation of downstream data product creation, especially considering the large data volumes that need to be processed. Practical and efficient solutions for structuring and cataloging data in a machine-readable format are of great importance. Specifically, the relationship between DOIs and related datasets is often not represented in common knowledge graphs, making machine-based reuse more challenging.

The hope is that these challenges can be addressed with the help of the new FAIRCORE4EOSC components, significantly improving the efficiency of data processing and reuse. For example, these components could help better integrate provenance information and promote the automation of data workflows.

In relation to the existing user requirements in this Case Study and opportunities for improvement regarding the underlying infrastructure, the RAiD component was selected as a promising repository for project contexts and other research activities. The DTR component was identified as a useful service for storing definitions of machine-readable data description profiles. The MSCR component is considered a potential tool for the conversion of type definitions – also machine-actionable. Additionally, the PIDGraph and RDGraph components were chosen as tools for searching research data and their dependencies.

² Main website for the Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling project, <https://is.enes.org/index.html>

³ Climate4Impact website, <https://www.climate4impact.eu>

⁴ The Copernicus Climate Change Service website, <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu>

2.1.2 Achieved Integrations

Thanks to the new FAIRCORE4EOSC components, several workflows within the ENES infrastructure have a significant opportunity to be substantially improved in the future. However, not all components are yet guaranteed to offer their services in a reliable production mode in the future, so the improvements should be considered provisional for now.

Figure 1 roughly illustrates which components are used and their benefits.

Figure 1: Component benefits overview

ENES provides data and provenance information for a given dataset PID. The lowest level of ENES data are data files associated with Handle PIDs⁵. These data associated PIDs are linked to higher granularity data collections to which DOIs are assigned. DOIs are referenced in the scientific literature. DOIs are harvested and available as part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components PIDGraph and RDGraph. DOIs are also associated with specific research activities registered as RAiD identifiers. The PID metadata definition of ENES PIDs is registered as part of the Data Type Registry and provides machine parsing methods – also important for processing large data volumes. This definition associates Handle PIDs with DOIs and also RAiDs. Using the MSCR, it's possible to analyse different PID metadata definitions by synchronising them into one template, making them easier to compare. In addition, these analyses could be made machine-actionable, enabling work on large volumes of data.

The integration of FAIRCORE4EOSC services provides a broader view of the data used. This is due to the additional RAiD information, as well as the machine-aided evaluation options using PIDGraph, DTR and MSCR.

The following sections describe in more detail how the individual components have been used.

⁵ The Handle.Net Registry website, <https://handle.net/>

The use of RAiD as a central repository for project information has been successfully tested. Specifically, ENES and CMIP (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project)⁶ projects, along with associated research activities, have been registered in RAiD. It was also possible to map the dependencies between these projects. Research outcomes could be stored as project outputs, and activities from model centers could be recorded as project inputs. However, there is currently a limitation on the number of these in- and output flows in the related identifier section per RAiD⁷. A test showed that currently about 330 are possible. CMIP6 for example had an outcome of around 12 million datasets. The challenge is to provide an adequate storage capacity on the part of RAiD. On the other hand, the CMIP6 project must decide how the associated project outcomes can be divided, for instance, through subprojects. The RAiD team is already working on improving this.

The RAiD service shows great potential for the Climate Community. By linking data with projects and research activities, a variety of contextual information can be provided, such as connections between data and model centers, data and supporting institutions, data and involved individuals, or data and web presences. This facilitates researchers' ability to access information about the stakeholders involved in the data they are using, information they previously had to gather independently.

The Climate Community has to decide how and where data and RAiD relation should be integrated. One option would be to assign them via RAiD in- and outputs, but this becomes difficult to manage due to often large dataset outcomes – as previously outlined. Another possibility is to manage this additional information through DOIs, although not all research datasets have a DOI reference. Therefore, the preferred approach is to use the data type definitions from the DTR for this assignment.

The DTR has already been tested and evaluated in this regard. Specifically, ENES data types have been implemented, such as a CMIP6 data definition with references to datasets and data files, as well as an ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation)⁸ Handle definition as a DTR profile⁹. For the project reference, the corresponding RAiD has been added. When loading data using these DTR profiles, the user now has access to both the data and the project-specific data context. It is still unclear how to manage situations where the project reference spans multiple topics and is not just a simple project dependency in a tree structure. How should such projects be summarized? The solution of naming and adding the involved projects individually was successfully tested having 50 project dependencies in maximum. However, this is not the optimal approach, as the number of projects that can be added to the DTR definition is limited as well.

The use of DTR definitions was also tested in the context of a machine-driven analysis. Through central registration and validation against the used data, it was possible to successfully extract climate data and present it as a simple graph. The data type definitions through the DTR have proven to be very promising.

Another use of the DTR involved providing registered CF (Climate and Forecast)¹⁰ variables and their physical units as DTR types¹¹. This test was successful but was postponed due to clarification regarding responsibilities for CF. Finally, the definition of a NetCDF file as a DTR MIME type¹² was tested. This definition is intended to

⁶ The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project website, <https://wcrp-cmip.org/>

⁷ Kruess, B. (2025). Climate Change case study: RAiD, DTR and MSCR definitions (V1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019497>

⁸ The Earth System Grid Federation, <https://esgf.llnl.gov/mission.html>

⁹ Kruess, B. (2025). Climate Change case study: RAiD, DTR and MSCR definitions (V1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019497>

¹⁰ The CF metadata conventions website, <https://cfconventions.org/>

¹¹ Kruess, B. (2025). Climate Change case study: RAiD, DTR and MSCR definitions (V1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019497>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019497>, example available in Appendix I: DTR type: application/netcdf definition

complement the CMIP6 and ESGF data definitions, particularly regarding the machine-readable file format of the data files associated with individual datasets. The corresponding test was also successful.

PIDGraph and RDGraph were compared based on their search results for a set of sample data. Both now support RAiD. However, within the scope of the Climate Change Case Study, the focus was primarily directed towards PIDGraph, as it enables querying the association of RAiD to DOI via the GraphQL interface. This functionality was examined as another application case. The "related identifier" section in PIDGraph presents all relations associated with a DOI, including the linked RAiD information. As previously discussed, a decision is still pending regarding how data and RAiD should be integrated within the community moving forward. The conducted PIDGraph check utilized the DOI mapping, which proved to be effective and is particularly well-suited for all DOI-associated datasets. The RAiD information obtained in this manner was subsequently analyzed in the context of the project framework and used as an enhancement to the existing data provenance within ENES. The user is thus provided with the DOI as a citation reference along with the associated RAiD information, which serves as a source for entities such as model centers and funding agencies. The aspect of automation was also taken into account during testing. GraphQL is machine-readable as an API, enabling its use in automated workflows.

The MSCR was originally intended to be used as a "translator" for different communities, allowing users without expertise in climate modeling to understand the work of a climate scientist. Another key use case, which involves using MSCR as a metadata translator, is particularly relevant for data maintenance. For example, MSCR was used to translate an internal metadata format for ESGF data into a specific CMIP6 metadata format¹³. This could make the need to adjust the data maintenance software obsolete. This potential is promising, as it may help avoid significant development efforts for data management software in the future.

2.1.3 Outlook

The availability and reliability of the required components in the productive environment are crucial. The operational services behind must not only be cost-effective and tailored to the needs of climate research, but also scalable, reliable and trustworthy. Most importantly, they must be sustainable in the long term. Once this has been confirmed and paths for further development exist, it may be possible to consider other new user stories.

RAiD has the potential to become a central repository for projects and their details. Having everything in one place makes this service so interesting. For large projects with many dependencies, a decision must be made on how such an information network can be divided among different projects or subprojects. It is also still unclear how to handle project stakeholders – as institutions, authors, and role holders – who do not have an ORCID id or ROR id. Additionally, related objects that are PIDless cannot yet be entered. Unfortunately, there is currently no proper user management system in place. Managing user rights for a given RAiD is essential. Many users are expected to require this feature. It must be possible to share the maintenance of RAiDs between institutions or individuals, or to delegate this responsibility to third parties.

The DTR has proven its usability as a data type repository and validation tool. This is particularly important for machine-assisted analyses and evaluations. It facilitates the handling of large data volumes. Evaluation software can thus be significantly simplified, as it can read and interpret the data to be evaluated through their associated DTR definitions. Both the data and the definitions may change. However, the software does not need to be modified to accommodate new data or definitions. It is now feasible to transition several data management software applications, as well as existing analysis software, to utilize DTR types. Another approach is to leverage the DTR for data typing of STAC (SpatioTemporal Assets Catalogs¹⁴ defined as FDOs

¹³ Kruess, B. (2025). Climate Change case study: RAiD, DTR and MSCR definitions (V1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019497>

¹⁴ The SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs website, <https://stacspect.org/en>

(FAIR Digital Objects)¹⁵, thereby facilitating enhanced interoperability across data spaces in climate science, which is part of work package 3 “Tackling the data challenge”¹⁶ within ESIWACE3 (3rd phase of the Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe)¹⁷. The initiative was presented at the FAIRfest in The Hague¹⁸.

PIDGraph and RDGraph are promising tools for the discovery and retrieval of research data. The PIDGraph offers advanced capabilities for machine-assisted search and data extraction through its GraphQL interface. The RDGraph, on the other hand, is particularly well suited to non-community users thanks to its natural language search functionality, which allows for a more intuitive search experience. Nevertheless, significant progress is still needed in this area to optimise the effectiveness and accessibility. Unfortunately, it cannot be used properly at the moment.

Utilizing the MSCR facilitates the analysis of various Persistent Identifier metadata definitions by consolidating them into a unified template, which enhances their comparability. Furthermore, such analyses can be rendered machine-actionable, thereby enabling the processing and management of large volumes of data efficiently. The idea of using MSCR for data maintenance software seems valuable. A detailed investigation is necessary to identify all potential areas where this component could be applied.

2.2 Social Sciences and Humanities

2.2.1 Community challenges and objectives

The Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) Case Study is defined around three services used in the CLARIN¹⁹ infrastructure. (1) The Virtual Collection Registry (VCR), which is a registry where users can create and manage virtual collections. A virtual collection is a collection of references to data stored across repositories. For each collection and for each reference in a collection some metadata is collected. The collections are assigned a DOI when published for easy citation. (2) The Switchboard, which is an explorative service to find what tools in our domain can be used on a data object. It acts as a broker between the data and the tools. A user will upload or provide a link to some data to the Switchboard. After analyzing the data, a tool selection is made based on properties such as data type, language and encoding. Finally, the (3) Digital Object Gateway (DOG) is an abstraction layer or API into the outside world. It offers a uniform interface to access digital objects across various persistent identifier (PID) systems and repositories. The user of DOG does not need to know the specifics of how to access one particular data repository. Instead, by sending the identifier of an object, typically the landing page, to the DOG, the DOG can perform a range of standard operations to explore and process the object.

A number of example use cases are used to illustrate the challenges in our domain. (1) A teacher preparing materials for a lecture is using virtual collections. By distributing a virtual collection, all students can easily access all materials required for the lecture. The process of creating a collection can be a bit tedious as all links are added manually including the required metadata that has to be filled in. The collection creation workflow is improved by filling in as much information as possible in an automated way. (2) The example of a researcher looking for tools to process a data collection is another use case. The researcher has a set of files

¹⁵ The Fair Digital Objects Forum website, <https://fairdo.org/>

¹⁶ Kulüke, M., Peters-von Gehlen, K., & Anders, I. (2025). Deliverable D3.5 - Report on domain-specific FDO standard. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14752859>

¹⁷ The Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe website, <https://www.esiwace.eu/>

¹⁸ Widmann, H., Anders, I., Kulüke, M., Kruess, B., & Peters-von Gehlen, K. (2025, März 11). Interoperability between Data Spaces in Climate Science: Using DTR to specify STAC Catalogs defined as FDO. FAIRfest: Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOSC, Den Haag, The Netherlands, 20–21 February 2025. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15006719>

¹⁹ The Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure website, <https://www.clarin.eu/>

and is interested in what tools are available in the CLARIN infrastructure to process these files. A script, interfacing with the switchboard API²⁰, is used to iterate over the files and each file is sent to the switchboard for processing. The collected responses can be used to review the available tools. This workflow can be improved with better data typing, which results in a higher quality tool suggestion.

In addition to the challenges that follow from the example use cases, alternatives to further increase the usability of our services and improve the discoverability of our data also need to be investigated.

This Case Study integrates with the following FAIRCORE4EOSC components: PIDMR, DTR, MSCR, PIDGraph and RDGraph.

2.2.2 Achieved Integrations

The interaction between the CLARIN services and FAIRCORE4EOSC components is shown on a high level in Figure 2. These are the integrations implemented in this Case Study. Each integration will be discussed in detail in the following sections.

Figure 2: Overview of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components in the CLARIN infrastructure

The DTR is integrated with both the Virtual Collection registry and the Digital Object Gateway. The Switchboard and to a lesser extent the Virtual Collection Registry make use of digital object media types. A number of examples have been observed where the existing IANA media types lack utility for certain functions. The existing media types are not always specific enough in e.g. not specifying a schema and lack taxonomy support beyond the type / subtype relation. An ExtendedMimeType has been defined in the DTR to overcome these issues.

²⁰ The Switchboard PUBLIC API Specification, <https://github.com/clarin-eric/switchboard-doc/blob/master/documentation/PublicAPI.md>

The Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) ExtendedMimeType is a concrete example. This ExtendedMimeType provides an alias to the original type, a set of links to the RFC, official schema and MSCR schema and crosswalks. It also is associated with a taxonomy node.

The Virtual Collection Registry is using the DTR, together with the MSCR, to improve the workflow to add a link to a collection. When a user adds a link to a collection, the media type returned by the HTTP response is used to query the DTR for ExtendedMimeTypes with that media type as an alias. If an ExtendedMimeType is found, the associated schema information is used for further interaction with the MSCR. This interaction between the VCR and DTR for the case where an ExtendedMimeType and crosswalk are found is illustrated in the interaction diagram in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Interaction diagram describing the integration between VCR, DTR and MSCR

In addition the Digital Object Gateway is using the DTR to return taxonomy information associated with the provided ExtendedMimeType²¹. The Digital Object Gateway can then be used to query for more generic or more specific ExtendedMimeTypes, based on the taxonomy structure. An example is the “application/tei+xml → text/xml → text taxonomy”²². While only a few tools in the Switchboard Tool Inventory²³ that operate on

²¹ Elbers, W. (2025). FAIRCORE4EOSC SSH Case Study DTR Types [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15000074>

²² Elbers, W. (2025). FAIRCORE4EOSC SSH Case Study DTR Types [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15000074>. Example available in Appendix II: DTR type: application/tei+xml definition

²³ The Switchboard Tool Inventory, <https://switchboard.clarin.eu/tools>

TEI²⁴ directly are supported, more generic tools can also be suggested by utilizing the taxonomy data. Currently such an example will work for the more technical users that are able to script against the DOG and Switchboard directly.

The MSCR is a very interesting service, relevant to the Virtual Collection Registry. Improving the collection creation workflow is one of the goals illustrated by use case (1) in the section on community challenges and objectives. When a link is added by URI, it can be a URL to a digital object (landing page, metadata, or resource) or a persistent identifier (e.g., hdl:20.500.14106/1328 as used in the collection <https://doi.org/10.34733/vc-1109>). The page is analyzed, and enough information is extracted to automatically fill the metadata fields for the collection link. This is already supported for metadata in our domain, CMDI. Extending this to other domains and, thus, other metadata schemas will greatly improve this workflow.

In the Virtual Collection Registry backend any link added to a collection is analyzed in order to extract the associated schema if it exists and there is a strategy to extract it. If there is no schema found, because the URI does not point to a metadata file or the metadata file schema is unknown, the fallback strategy is for the user to provide all relevant metadata – the worst case workflow. If a schema is identified, the MSCR will be queried by the VCR backend to find crosswalks with the identified schema as the source and a fixed Dublin Core (DC) schema as the target. If a crosswalk exists the associated XSLT file is downloaded and used to convert the source metadata into the DC format. This is a known format that can be used to extract the relevant data, which is then used to populate the user interface automatically. This is also illustrated in the interaction between the VCR and MSCR in the interaction diagram in figure 4.

This approach combines with the DTR integration as well. There is no requirement for an XML metadata file to define its schema. While good for machine processability, the schema information cannot solely be relied upon to be linked from the metadata object itself. In these cases, the DTR can be queried for an ExtendedMimeType, and the linked schema information in the DTR can be used to query the MSCR for a crosswalk.

Figure 4 is a screenshot illustrating the implementation of the algorithm described. The screenshot shows a technical representation of the underlying algorithm, highlighting the mapped data type, crosswalk, the description and name fields extracted via the MSCR crosswalk.

The third service relevant to this Case Study is the PIDMR. Both the Virtual Collection Registry and Digital Object Gateway are obvious candidates to integrate with the PIDMR. Both services already support Handles and DOIs. When adding links to a virtual collection, resolving the handle to the underlying resource and making sure the user is using a PID if it exists for the resource are both important. Before integrating with the PIDMR both the Handle and DOI PID systems were supported as these are most common in our domain. Since the PIDMR integration, the number of supported PID systems has increased substantially, further strengthening the cross domain usability of the Virtual Collection Registry. Table 2 lists 10 of the most relevant new PID systems for our Case Study but more importantly it shows that not each PID system offers the same functionality. Some systems can resolve to a landing page only, others can also resolve to the metadata object or to the resource itself. All of these are accepted when adding a link to a virtual collection. The Digital Object Gateway aims to explore the information behind a landing page, thus any PID system that can offer the metadata or resource directly fits well into this approach.

²⁴ The Text Encoding Initiative website, <https://tei-c.org/>

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https://lids.ling-phil.ox.ac.uk/lids/xmlui/bitstream/handle/20.500.14106/A39119/A39119.xml
A39119.xml
Suggested value
A vindication of the letter out of the north concerning Bishop Lake's declaration of his dying in the belief of the doctrine of passive obedience, &c. : in answer to a late pamphlet, called, The defence of the profession, &c. of the said Bishop : as far as it concerns the person of quality.

Suggested value
2025-02-48 10:12:04  PARSE_HTTP KEY_HTTP_RESPONSE_MEDIA_TYPE text/xml
2025-02-48 10:12:04  PARSE_HTTP HTTP_RESPONSE_CODE 200
2025-02-48 10:12:04  PARSE_HTTP NAME A39119.xml
2025-02-48 10:12:05  PARSE_CMDI STATE OK
2025-02-48 10:12:05  PARSE_MSCR STATE OK
2025-02-48 10:12:05  PARSE_MSCR NAME Eyre, William, 1612 or 13-1670.
2025-02-48 10:12:05  PARSE_MSCR DESCRIPTION A vindication of the letter out of the north concerning Bishop Lake's declaration of his dying in the belief of the doctrine of passive obedience, &c. : in answer to a late pamphlet, called, The defence of the profession, &c. of the said Bishop : as far as it concerns the person of quality.
2025-02-48 10:12:05  PARSE_MSCR PROCESS_0 performParsingDtr
2025-02-48 10:12:05  PARSE_MSCR PROCESS_1 Found datatype with id: 21.T11969/710b1a3647d431e205e0
2025-02-48 10:12:05  PARSE_MSCR PROCESS_2 Found crosswalk with id: 21.T13999/EOSC-202501000349738
    
```

Figure 4: Screenshot of the technical integration of the DTR and MSCR into the VCR.

The use of PIDs as persistent references in a collection is being advocated as much as possible in the Virtual Collection Registry. When a collection is cited, its PID should be used, and when links are added to a collection, the link PID should also be used if it exists. Sometimes, links are added to a collection directly via URL by our users. In these cases, it is preferred to check if a known PID points to this URL, and if so, a suggestion should be made to the user to use the PID instead.

Identifier System	DOG	PIDMR
HDL (with registered CLARIN repository, see list at ²)	L,M,R'	
HDL	L	
HDL, EPIC (21.*)		M, L
HDL, EPIC (old)		M, L
ARK		M, L
URN:NBN:DE		M, L
URN:NBN:FI		L
URN:NBN:NL		L
URN:NBN:CH		M, L, R
ORCID		L
arXiv		M, L, R
Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo)	L,M,R'	M, L, R
ISLRN		L
DOI	L,M,R'	M, L, R
B2SHARE	L,M,R'	

Table 2: Overview of supported PID systems in the DOG and PIDMR.

Where: M = Metadata, return the metadata associated with the identifier. L = Landing Page, return / redirect to the page where the identifier points to. R = Resource, this resolves to the resource

The process of looking up a PID for any given URL is called a reverse lookup, as opposed to a normal lookup, which is defined as the process of returning the URL associated with a PID. This feature was marked as out of scope of the PIDMR. This heavily depends on functionality offered by the PID system and most systems currently do not offer this.

Finally this Case Study is also using the PIDGraph and RDGraph. Both are used as explorative tools in our infrastructure. DOIs are minted for virtual collections to ensure easy citability. The metadata stored in the collection DOIs has been evaluated, and one of the gaps that have been identified is the missing ORCID identifiers for collection creators and authors. The Virtual Collection Registry user interface has been extended to collect ORCID identifiers and store them in the collection DOIs to improve their discoverability. This automatically propagates into the RDGraph as well and ensures a better discoverability in both graphs. During the course of the project, it has been discovered that the PIDGraph API supports reverse lookups for DOIs. Initially, some concerns were raised regarding usage limitations, but these have been increased considerably. While this is not a complete solution for the reverse lookup requirement, workflow improvements can be achieved if the DOI can already be suggested when the URL of an object is entered by the user.

2.2.3 Outlook

It turns out that the PIDGraph, via the DataCite API, supports reverse lookups for DOIs. This does not offer a reverse lookup solution for multiple PID systems, but being able to suggest our users to use a DOI instead of the URL is already an improvement. In addition to using the API, the PIDGraph also offers data dumps which could be used to cache the reverse lookup functionality locally. The reverse lookup functionality in the API is an interesting option for us to implement to offer at least a partial solution that covers DOIs. If the limits in the API, which have already been increased, prove to be an issue, the data dumps can be used to optimize the API usage.

Some concerns exist for all services regarding their sustainability, but the amount of uncertainty varies. Some services, such as the DTR, PIDGraph, and RDGraph, are based on existing solutions with organizations already supporting them before this project. Other services, such as the MSCR and PIDMR, have been newly developed, making it less clear at the time of writing how their sustainability is guaranteed. It is felt that there is a direct relation between the sustainability of a service and its uptake by communities and users. For the Case Study, this has meant that the integrations have been implemented in alpha and beta instances. Additionally the FAIRCORE4EOSC integrations are implemented in a fallback approach where possible as described in more detail in the Virtual Collection Registry workflow in the MSCR section. This allows for an alternative if a FAIRCORE4EOSC component is unavailable.

The MSCR is a very promising service. However its uptake is important for the relevance in our Case Study. The chance of finding a useful crosswalk is directly related to the number of registered schemas and crosswalks. Since this is one of the newly developed services there have been some usability issues both on the API side and usability of the UI side. This was expected and both have matured towards the end of the project.

2.3 Mathematics

2.3.1 Community challenges and objectives

This Case Study focuses on advancing data integration, metadata management, and knowledge graph development to better serve the mathematical research community. By collaborating with DataCite, OpenAIRE, and other key stakeholders, the team is working to ensure that mathematical data and research outputs are more accessible, interoperable, and compliant with global metadata standards. The Case Study is built around several core components:

- 🔄 Integration with the RSAC:

- Leveraging advancements from WP6 to improve metadata exposure and interoperability, supported by collaboration with the RSAC.
- Collaboration with PIDGraph:
 - Ensuring that mathematical research outputs are properly integrated into the PIDGraph, enabling persistent identification and improved discoverability.
- RDGraph Progress:
 - Enhancing the RDGraph to expose mathematical metadata effectively, resolving mapping challenges, and preparing registration of the zbMATH OAI service as a data provider for OpenAIRE.
- MSCR:
 - Expose the metadata formats and crosswalks in the MSCR
- Mathematical Knowledge Graph and DTR:
 - Expose the mathematical knowledge graph into the Data Type Registry (DTR) to provide a structured and scalable framework for managing mathematical data.
- PIDMR:
 - zbMATH and swMATH identifiers are resolvable with the PIDMR.

All of these efforts are designed to address the unique needs of mathematicians, enabling them to access, share, and build upon mathematical research outputs more effectively. By improving metadata quality, interoperability, and integration with global research infrastructures, this Case Study aims to empower mathematicians with the tools and resources they need to advance their work and collaborate more efficiently across disciplines.

2.3.2 Achieved Integrations

This Case Study integrates six components, each contributing to advancing metadata management, interoperability, and sustainability in mathematical research. The team is addressing metadata compliance and ingestion challenges through collaboration with key initiatives like PIDGraph, supported by DataCite, and RDGraph, backed by OpenAIRE, where efforts have focused on validation and resolving mapping issues. Research software sustainability is enhanced through integration with the RSAC, while the exposure of the Mathematics Subject Classification into the DTR, supported by GWDG, and progress on MSCR mappings, led by CSC, further strengthen the project's impact. The PIDMR is also supported by GRNET and has been integrated to resolve the zbMATH and swMATH persistent identifiers. This is schematically shown in Figure 5. Together, these components drive the team closer to achieving seamless metadata exposure and integration across systems.

The ongoing collaboration with the PIDGraph team and advancements in metadata integration offer substantial benefits to the mathematics community. By ensuring compliance with DataCite's metadata guidelines and resolving final configuration issues, the Mathematics Case Study team is enhancing the accessibility and interoperability of mathematical research data, especially providing identifier mappings between zbMATH identifiers and DOIs. This progress not only facilitates the ingestion of metadata into the PIDGraph but also strengthens the global visibility of mathematical resources, enabling researchers to connect and build upon existing work more effectively.

The significant strides made in the RDGraph, including resolving metadata mapping challenges and completing validation rounds with OpenAIRE, pave the way for seamless integration into the RDGraph. This will empower mathematicians with a richer, more interconnected knowledge base, fostering collaboration and innovation across the discipline.

Furthermore, the integration of the RSAC and collaboration with the RSAC underscore a commitment to software sustainability and improved metadata exposure, ensuring long-term usability and impact. Interoperability is significantly enhanced through the crosswalk to CodeMeta developed in this work package,

alongside the crosswalks created for the PIDGraph and RDGraph, all of which will be registered in the MSCR. This underscores a forward-thinking approach to structuring and sharing mathematical knowledge, ensuring greater accessibility and integration across systems. The Mathematical Subject Classification (MSC), a domain-specific knowledge graph for mathematics, is registered and typed into the Data Type Registry (DTR). Interoperability and consistency across mathematical resources are further enhanced by the integration of the PIDMR, which is used to resolve persistent identifiers for zbMATH and swMATH.

Collectively, these efforts promise to elevate the mathematics community's ability to discover, share, and utilize research outputs, driving progress in the field.

Figure 5: Schematic overview of the FAIRCORE4EOSC components in the MATH Case Study.

2.3.3 Outlook

Looking ahead, the team will continue refining metadata and OAI server configurations to ensure full compliance with DataCite guidelines, with a focus on achieving seamless ingestion into the PIDGraph and enhancing metadata quality in alignment with community standards. Efforts will also prioritize finalizing RDGraph ingestion, addressing remaining metadata mapping challenges, and conducting further OpenAIRE validation rounds to ensure robust metadata exposure. Collaboration with the RSAC will deepen, notably improving metadata exposure and interoperability, supported by ongoing engagement with the RSAC. The team will keep updated the mathematical knowledge graph into the DTR, establishing a more structured and scalable framework for managing mathematical data, which will serve as a foundation for future extensions and integrations. Additionally, the team will expose and maintain up-to-date crosswalks and formats related to CodeMeta, DataCite, and OpenAIRE within the MSCR. Collaboration with the PIDMR will be maintained to keep our identifiers or new identifiers resolvable. Overall, the team remains committed to advancing these initiatives, emphasizing scalability, interoperability, and alignment with community standards to drive progress in the field.

2.4 European Integration of National-level Services

2.4.1 Community challenges and objectives

National-level systems that collect information from CRISs (current research information systems) can be invaluable sources of data for e.g. research assessment, science policy making or to highlight EOSC-related contributions. However, the CRIS domain is struggling to achieve proper interoperability and data exchange between the different systems on institutional-, national- and pan-European levels. This has led to a situation where proper curation of metadata in institutional CRIS is not fully exploited, even though substantial work, of researchers and research administration alike, is being put into making data as good as possible both in coverage and metadata quality. Many systems already provide integrations to aggregate the data of institutional CRISs to a national level, making way for national research graphs trying to provide a broader view on the research – one where people, projects and research grants among many other inputs, provide for publications, activities and datasets as outputs of research. These different entities hold many interlinking connections between them and is essentially what the research graphs are trying to make visible.

For the European Integration of National-level Services Case Study, three different services were chosen to highlight the potential of CRIS-like information from the research graph and integration perspectives. These were: Research.fi²⁵ and Publinova. Research.fi is a Finnish national CRIS system developed by CSC - IT Center For Science and funded by the Ministry of Science and Education in Finland that aggregates information from various local CRIS and funders' systems²⁶. Publinova is a Dutch national platform for the universities of applied sciences to 'connect practice-based research to the world, and to increase the impact of practice-based science'²⁷, launched in 2023 and steadily growing in coverage and maturity. It is used for this case-study because the development of the planned and proposed Open Knowledge Base was cancelled.

To enhance these research graphs within services, the PIDGraph and RDGraph components were chosen to provide further information on the possible links between different research entities. These included e.g. PID to PID connections from datasets to publications and possible research grants connected to organisations and/or people. Depending on the CRIS systems, these connections might be difficult to convey to local systems without such integrations making the aggregation work.

One such expansion in handling research graphs is also the community's need for tracking research projects and activities. These entities usually vary in time and scope, much more than other research entities, meaning that the research projects are often best observed via both the research inputs (people, organizations, research grants) or by their outputs (publications, activities, datasets). RAiD is being established as a standard PID for handling this research project information, but the uptake needs to happen in local CRIS systems as well as those that are usually the closest source to the actual information, i.e. the researchers themselves.

The European Integration of National-level Services Case Study also explored the possibilities to handle information on research related software and source code through the practices developed by Software Heritage service. As it currently stands, the CRIS systems might have this sort of entity already in place in some form already, but the metadata and the data model behind it usually are rather incompatible from Software Heritage's point of view, as Software Heritage currently lacks providing research related PIDs on e.g. people (ORCID) or organizations (ROR) making proper research graph difficult to observe and maintain.

In Europe, there have been endeavours like the Common European Research Information Format (CERIF), developed by the euroCRIS organization, which is an information model "intended to support interchange of

²⁵ Research.fi website, <https://research.fi/>

²⁶ Developing Research Information Hub in Finland, a view from the Ministry <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.044>

²⁷ About Publinova, <https://publinova.nl/en/about>

research information between and with CRISs²⁸. Refactoring the more than a decade old CERIF data model has been one of the goals for the European Integration of National-level Services Case Study. The new model currently provides the Core, and further additional modules have been planned, e.g. Persons²⁹. Although the refactoring project has been running since 2021, the current CERIF model is still used in many contexts, e.g. OpenAIRE utilizes the current CERIF standard for harvesting CRIS-like information as noted in the Guidelines for CRIS Managers³⁰. One issue on making the CERIF have a wider uptake has been the laborious mapping work, as CERIF is seldom used as a basis for CRISs³¹ internal data model, but rather as a conceptual model. On making the data exchanges happen, integrations have to be usually mapped between various data models. One key objective for the Case Study has been the utilization of MSCR to both register current CRISs data models, but also have the refactored CERIF2 as a CRIS domain's de facto data model, where CRIS managers could use it to achieve proper crosswalks between CRIS systems. In ideal cases this would mean only one mapping from one system to the central refactored CERIF2 model to then achieve data exchange possibilities between all other systems that have done the mapping as well – enabling the crosswalk for the CRIS community via MSCR. Also the work within the Case Study could be utilized as a template for further integration of CRIS systems within EOSC.

2.4.2 Achieved Integrations

The European Integration of National-level Service Case Study had major use cases for five of the components developed in FAIRCORE4EOSC. These are shown in Figure 6 for each corresponding component. Each of the component specific integrations is described in the following section one component at a time. As European Integration of National-level Services includes three different national systems, any integrations are expressed by the individual systems included within the Case Study.

Figure 6: High level view of integrations regarding European Integration of National-level Services Case Study and the key use cases for each component developed in FAIRCORE4EOSC project..

For Research.fi, the PIDGraph component integration is based on the data dump ingestion and loading it to the Research.fi local database. The Datacite's API layer, including the GraphQL solution, was first tested

²⁸ Common European Research Information Format, <https://eurocris.org/services>

²⁹ The CERIF Core specification, <https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core>

³⁰ OpenAIRE Guidelines for CRIS Managers, <https://openaire-guidelines-for-cris-managers.readthedocs.io/en/v1.2.0/>

but after dialogue with the DataCite's component team, the data dump was chosen as the most stable solution for Research.fi needs. The data dump from DataCite got enhancements during the FAIRCORE4EOSC project following the feedback from the Research.fi development team, e.g. inclusion of CrossRef DOIs in the data dump in addition to DataCite DOIs, which improved the matching of data and the possibility to filter out information based on ROR identifiers for country specific data. Research.fi had three relevant use cases for PIDGraph data: 1) Ingestion of PID to PID connections between research objects, especially concerning research datasets, 2) Loading abstract information on publications within Research.fi, which were missing and 3) Use DataCite's relation type information to enhance Research.fi's support for relation types in general. These were achieved during the FAIRCORE4EOSC with the exception of relation type development, which is still under development³². Current Research.fi PIDGraph integration is being prepared to move into the production phase, where the ETL-process is being optimized for multiprocessing and data writing strategies to maintain the automatic loading of new and updated data from DataCite.

RDGraph integration has been prepared during the FAIRCORE4EOSC project with minor alteration to the schedule, as the use cases regarding Research.fi to enhance research graph information from OpenAIRE's side is expected to happen only after the project is finished. OpenAIRE is currently harvesting the Research.fi API layer for research grant information, but ongoing work is expanding to also make use of publication data, open research calls and research dataset information – all entities are available in Research.fi in its internal data model in JSON format. This included OpenAIRE to be granted API layer access to Research.fi in 2024, as there is a formal approval process for the Research.fi API layer access to be granted by the Ministry of Science and Culture in Finland. The original plan to use either refactored CERIF2 or older CERIF format was abandoned, and instead there was a mapping exercise to utilise Research.fi data.

For the RAiD component, the work for Research.fi has greatly benefited from the national Hankehaavi research projects repository in Finland, that was maintained by 6 research organizations in Finland and abandoned in 2023 before moving to Research.fi. As such, the Research.fi has piloted the development of research project information with the Hankehaavi data acting as seed data. This allowed both to explore and enhance the upcoming Research.fi national data model for research projects to be based both on already available information from research organizations, but also to heavily benefit from the developed RAiD schema. This development included difficulties on e.g. maintaining data with no PIDs (on creators, organisations etc.) that largely remain in historical data (projects start dates span from late 1900s to 2023) for Hankehaavi. During the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, the national data model got improved in such ways that it is compatible with the RAiD schema but yet has some national flavours on e.g. classifications included. During the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, the Research.fi team built the technical solution for interacting with the RAiD API layer. This includes the ability to both mint RAiDs for research projects in Research.fi, but also update RAiD metadata with updates from Research.fi. In early 2025, Research.fi was updated with more than 11 000 research projects based on the Hankehaavi information, which are displayed as a BETA feature³³. The research project information is still static, as integrations with Finnish local CRIS systems are expected to happen later. Also the research projects haven't been minted with RAiDs as the governance model and policies for RAiD are still discussed with national research organizations in Finland before wider uptake is possible.

Publinova has focused on applying RAiD to improve the registration and exchange of project information between local CRISs and Publinova, so that Publinova can display e.g. the grants, persons and publications for each project. That is largely an organizational challenge, for which the case study engaged with the applied science community to learn how their systems and processes can create and maintain RAiD identifiers. There is not yet a standard way in which the community records project information. Often, this is recorded locally using spreadsheets. Many of them are currently exploring how they can record project information centrally,

³² Piloting the use of PIDGraph data in Research.fi, *Procedia Computer Science*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.069>

³³ Research projects in the research.fi service, <https://research.fi/en/results/projects>

in an interoperable way. The case study had initiated a focused (on-going) Case Study with two institutes to explore in-depth how RAiD can be implemented in their organization and systems. In preparation, the case study integrated RAiD to the metadata schema of SURFsharekit (the repository used by many institutes of applied sciences), so that its contents can reference future projects with RAiD identifiers. The case study learned that RAiD focuses on recording contributors via ORCID. For the applied sciences institutes, and the recording of RAiD via CRISs, this raises two concerns: a) The adoption of ORCID is low, and many contributors are professionals and outside academia and b) if the researchers' participation in a project is confirmed via a CRIS, then researchers should not be asked to validate that contribution in the RAiD system again. and that researchers need to confirm their contribution to a project using their ORCID. Another identified challenge will be to avoid, or manage, redundant creation of RAiD records for the same project. This may happen if RAiD records are created by multiple partners of a project, or by both a CRIS and a service like Open Science Framework.

For Software Heritage integration, a small study was conducted on Research.fi's information on research software and the possible connections to what is included in Software Heritage. This study was conducted on the Software Heritage's API layer, where the origins data was used to search for both intrinsic and extrinsic metadata. The queries were based on Authors, URLs and any PIDs (most prominently DOIs) of the about 400 ICT applications metadata that were available in Research.fi. This study found out that only 4 matches were made between Research.fi metadata and Software Heritage, although more (31 in total) were identified by manual tests. The study revealed that Software Heritage is missing PID information on metadata of people (ORCID) and organizations (ROR), which limits the possibilities to match these to CRIS-like information. Based on this study, no concrete integration plans were put forward as most crucial information on PIDs (mainly ORCIDs and RORs) are still missing in Software Heritage metadata. Some preliminary planning was made on the possible future integration with Software Heritage on e.g. claiming information to personal research profiles in Research.fi, but these are not feasible in FAIRCORE4EOSC scope to achieve.

The MSCR component had multiple use cases for the Case Study of European Integration of National-level Services, with the most prominent being the ability to use refactored CERIF2 as de facto registered schema in MSCR to be utilized in any mapping exercise or data exchange needs within the CRIS community³⁴. For this work, the CERIF2 refactoring has advanced during the FAIRCORE4EOSC project's timespan with planned release to happen late in Spring 2025. The MSCR test instance was used to practice both registering the CERIF2 schema and Research.fi internal data model, while exploring the possibilities to map these two schemas within MSCR³⁵. The mapping was finished, but to further operationalize the mapping, a concrete data exchange need would have to arise from system to system. As a conceptual schema, the difficulties on mapping CERIF2 were also realized, as none of the planned CERIF2 community expansions have yet to be implemented. During FAIRCORE4EOSC, the possibilities of making these CERIF2 community expansions based on the Research.fi data model on research infrastructures or research activities as individual entities were explored, but not yet implemented in the CERIF2 project. As the MSCR production environment went so far into the FAIRCORE4EOSC project's timespan, the Research.fi data model or the CERIF2 models are still missing from MSCR but are expected to be updated there in near future. As such, also the status of possible crosswalks between CRIS systems based on CERIF2 cannot yet cover all the necessary information from Research.fi.

³⁴ Implementing interoperability - Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry approach to FAIR metadata mappings, [Proceedings of EUNIS 2024 annual congress in Athens](#), vol 105, pages 58-68, <https://doi.org/10.29007/khls>

³⁵ CRIS systems integration as a case study for the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry, *Procedia Computer Science* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.070>

The Publinova case study engaged with the applied sciences community to develop a metadata schema based on the refactored CERIF2³⁶ so that the information from forthcoming CRIS systems can easily interoperate with Publinova and other systems. The case study experimented with MSCR by registering the MODS schema, and creating mappings to CERIF2 based on NL profile used by repositories³⁷. The initial versions of MSCR could not define complex transformations (e.g. applying a filter on elements), but these are now supported in the latest version of MSCR. The case study is currently working on initial CERIF2-based sample serializations for Publinova that can be registered and crosswalked using MSCR.

2.4.3 Outlook

For PIDGraph the production phase for Research.fi integration is expected to be running after the FAIRCORE4EOSC project with future use cases planned, e.g. expanding the relation type classifications within Research.fi. The work has as such already expanded the data entity relation within Research.fi and, as such, greatly improved the Research.fi data content and Finnish affiliated research objects, which is made reusable by Finnish research organisations as well via the Research.fi API layer. One track is also to improve the practices in digesting information from the PIDGraph data dump to allow more lightweight solutions to be ran in the future.

RDGraph integration to Research.fi is expected to be finished in late Spring 2025 when the full extension of Research.fi information is harvested to OpenAIRE. After this initial phase, the possible use cases for RDGraph information to be used in the Research.fi context are to be explored, with some similarities to PIDGraph data ingestion. Especially interesting for Research.fi are any research objects that are affiliated to Finnish research organizations and would be missing from the current local sources for Research.fi, e.g. research grants of international research funders.

The SURF Open Research Information programme continues to promote and facilitate the usage of persistent identifiers and linking of entities in the Netherlands, thereby contributing to the PIDGraph. It is currently proposing, on behalf of all universities and unanimously endorsed by all rectors, plans to (a) improve governance, standards and PID adoption and interoperability across repositories, CRISs and infrastructures like OpenAIRE or EOSC RDGraph and (b) setting up a shared data lake architecture for efficient reuse and integration of this information to enable e.g. open science monitoring and responsible research evaluation.

For RAiD, uptake within Finland is moving ahead with the Research.fi steering group, led by the Ministry of Science and Culture in Finland, setting up a national working group for 2025-2027 consisting of people from various research organisations in Finland to support national endeavours to collect and jointly develop research projects information. This included both finalizing the national data model for research projects, heavily influenced by the RAiD schema, but also exploring the workflows in adopting RAiD in local CRIS systems and Research.fi. Hankehaavi-pilot data is to be used as a basis for Research.fi development regarding the working group's objectives.

For Publinova the RAiD Case Study with 2 applied science institutes runs in Q1 and Q2 of 2025. The outcomes will be shared and a follow-up towards implementation in the Dutch CRIS landscape will be planned, as there is great interest by research institutes in the Netherlands.

Work related to the uptake of MSCR is to be continued within the CRIS community. It is an important component for making CERIF2 as a crosswalkable domain specific schema. It can be further disseminated as

³⁶ Advice for Metadata standards and agreements in applied science (in Dutch).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12701230>

³⁷ Edustandaard Agreements for Bibliographic Metadata using MODS (in Dutch)

[Metadata Object Description Scheme \(MODS\) - Metadata Object Description Scheme versie 1.3 - Edustandaard](#)

a potential activity for e.g. euroCRIS events. Also the Research.fi and Publinova data models are to be expected for registration within MSCR to support interoperability also in national contexts regarding the source system integrations within Research.fi or Publinova.

2.5 Service Providers and Research Data Management Communities

2.5.1 Community challenges and objectives

The Case Study answers the general need of research communities for interoperable data services that facilitate discovery, access and reusability of research data. Researchers and data managers face challenges which can be expressed through the following questions;

- 🕒 How can I store, share & publish my research data and make it available to other researchers more easily?
- 🕒 How can I make an extensive and clear description of the data for better understanding of the research?
- 🕒 How can you make it easier to have metadata schemas for research communities to publish their data under the same community?
- 🕒 How can I find research data relevant and / or related to my research data?
- 🕒 What about related projects and their relationships?

To answer these questions and meet these requirements, EUDAT CDI B2SHARE and B2FIND will be enhanced and improved through the integration of the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), Data Type Registry (DTR), Research Discovery Graph (RDGraph) and Persistent Identifiers (PIDGraph), Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) and Compliance Assessment Tool (CAT) services and components. Research communities will benefit from the MSCR and DTR by being able to perform and validate the mapping of their specific metadata schemas to the EUDAT Extended and EUDAT core metadata schemas by themselves.

Figure 7: The connections of EUDAT services to FAIRCORE4EOSC services, focussing on EUDAT B2SHARE.

2.5.2 Achieved Integrations

The EUDAT B2SHARE core metadata schema has been made available in the MSCR and the DTR so it is easier to register, store, publish and share research data. The EUDAT Extended (B2SHARE) metadata schema has been successfully defined in the DTR using both the UI and REST API, making it easier to obtain

the data type definitions. EUDAT Extended (B2SHARE) and EUDAT Core (B2FIND) metadata schemas have been registered so that the community metadata could be retrieved in a future version of B2SHARE. MSCR is a very interesting service for B2FIND, too, as the possibility of referring to persistently identified metadata schemas and the possible collaborative editing of crosswalks reduces mapping- and communication efforts on both B2FIND and community side.

Figure 8: EUDAT extended schema as seen in DTR

EUDAT B2SHARE has incorporated different metadata identifier handles for the use of RDGraph, PIDGraph and RAiD;

- 🔗 Related identifier type metadata handles – DOI. Datacite DOIs are made available for the PIDGraph.
- 🔗 RAiD identifiers are created in the EUDAT B2SHARE root schema to allow researchers to be able to add references to other research activities and projects.
- 🔗 The provided identifiers are of the type of “Alternate Identifier” or as a “Related Identifier” which will give researchers the possibility to add necessary information on the relationships of the research to other research.

These metadata handles will make it easier to add better information on research and their relations to other research and projects.

```

Alternate identifier :: alternate_identifiers
The alternative identifiers for this resource such as a
URN, URI or an ISBN number.

alternate_identifier (required) string

Type ::
alternate_identifier_type
(required)
enum [ARK, arXiv, bibcode, DOI, EAN13, EISSN, Handle, ISBN, ISSN, ISTC, LISSN, LSID, ORCID, PMID,
PURL, UPC, URL, URN, w3id, RAID]
The type of the identifier.

Related identifiers :: related_identifiers
The identifiers of other resources related to the resource
such as a URN, URI or an ISBN number.

related_identifier (required) string

Resource type ::
resource_type_general
The type of the resource.
enum [Audiovisual, Book, BookChapter, Collection, ComputationalNotebook, ConferencePaper,
ConferenceProceeding, DataPaper, Dataset, Dissertation, Event, Image, InteractiveResource, Journal,
JournalArticle, Model, OutputManagementPlan, PeerReview, PhysicalObject, Preprint, Report, Service,
Software, Sound, Standard, Text, Workflow, Other]

Type :: related_identifier_type
(required)
enum [ARK, arXiv, bibcode, DOI, EAN13, EISSN, Handle, ISBN, ISSN, ISTC, LISSN, LSID, ORCID, PMID,
PURL, UPC, URL, URN, w3id, RAID]
The type of the identifier.

Relation :: relation_type
(required)
The relation type of the described
reference.
enum [IsCitedBy, Cites, IsSupplementTo, IsPublishedIn, IsSupplementedBy, IsContinuedBy, Continues,
HasMetadata, IsMetadataFor, IsNewVersionOf, IsPreviousVersionOf, IsPartOf, HasPart, IsReferencedBy,
References, IsDocumentedBy, Documents, IsCompiledBy, Compiles, IsVariantFormOf, IsOriginalFormOf,
IsIdenticalTo, IsReviewedBy, Reviews, IsDerivedFrom, IsSourceOf, Describes, IsDescribedBy, HasVersion,
IsVersionOf, Requires, IsRequiredBy, Obsoletes, IsObsoletedBy]

Scheme :: scheme string

Type :: related_identifier_type
(required)
enum [ARK, arXiv, bibcode, DOI, EAN13, EISSN, Handle, ISBN, ISSN, ISTC, LISSN, LSID, ORCID,
PURL, UPC, URL, URN, w3id, RAID]
The type of the identifier.
    
```

Figure 9: EUDAT B2SHARE metadata schema identifiers made available to RAiD, PIDGraph & RDGraph

B2SHARE exposes this enriched metadata to B2FIND. B2FIND in turn is harvested by OpenAire via OAI-PMH API and thus integrated into the RDGraph, thus ensuring the findability of the B2SHARE metadata within the RDGraph and subsequently the Resource Hub of the EOSC EU Node. B2FIND has also successfully tested using information from the PIDGraph such as displaying the citation count of a dataset and adding the related identifiers of the citing publications, or adding RAiDs as related identifiers to a metadata record. This helps users to decide on the relevance of their search results and to find related data sources.

Reconstruction of global land use and land cover AD 800 to 1992

This dataset contains reconstructions of land use and land cover from AD 800 to 1992 in global coverage at 30 minute resolution. After AD 1700, the data is based on Ramankutty and Foley (1999), Foley et al. (2003) and Klein Goldewijk (2001); for earlier times, land use is estimated with a country-based method that uses national population data (McEvedy and Jones, 1978) as a proxy for agricultural activity. For each year, a map is provided that contains 14 fields. Each field holds the fraction the respective vegetation type covers in the total grid cell (0-1). The vegetation types comprise three human land use types (crop, C3 pasture and C4 pasture) and 11 natural vegetation types (based on the potential vegetation map of Ramankutty and Foley, 1999). For the time period prior to AD 1700 two additional land cover scenarios are provided (scenmin and scenmax). They quantify the uncertainties associated with this approach, through technological progress in agriculture and uncertainties in population estimates. The additional datasets combine the known uncertainties in a way to give the most extreme range for possible estimates of land use area for each year before 1700. The datasets thus do not represent consistent time series of plausible alternative scenarios, but indicate, for each year, a maximum range outside which estimates of land use area are unrealistic. See citations and references for details. Vegetation types: 1 Tropical evergreen forest 2 Tropical deciduous forest 3 Temperate evergreen broadleaf forest 4 Temperate/boreal deciduous broadleaf forest 5 Temperate/boreal evergreen conifers 6 Temperate/boreal deciduous conifers 7 Raingreen shrubs 8 Summergreen shrubs 9 C3 natural grasses 10 C4 natural grasses 11 Tundra 12 Crop 13 C3 pasture 14 C4 pasture

Identifier	Value
DOI	https://doi.org/10.1594/WDCC/RECON_LAND_COVER_800-1992
Related Identifier	IsCitedBy https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14153777
Metadata Access	https://data.cloud.dlr.de/data/provider/

Figure 10: EUDAT B2FIND search result includes additional citation references from PIDGraph query.

A development version of the CAT toolkit was used to check EOSC PID compatibility of EUDAT CDI B2SHARE. The assessment result is shown in Figure 11. Tested production CAT toolkit to check EOSC PID compatibility. Minor adjustments needed to pass the full assessment.

Figure 11: CAT Assessment Result

2.5.3 Outlook

SPRDM will utilize the MSCR to create community definitions as well as updating community information in the future EUDAT B2SHARE. EUDAT B2SHARE will also utilize DTR as a source and storage for data types in its future versions. SPRDM will work to improve metadata handles for PIDGraph, RDGraph and RAiD and incorporate them into the future versions of EUDAT B2SHARE and will be propagated to EUDAT B2FIND.

3 Conclusion and recommendations

Each of the five Case Studies has reported on the integration work done with the FAIRCORE4EOSC components. The report will be concluded by summarizing the main benefits of each component and providing a number of recommendations.

For all the Case Studies, maturity and sustainability of the components are very important, especially before integrating any of these services in our production environments. Most of the integration work has been done in non-production environments. There was a big difference in terms of maturity between the offered components. Some are based on an existing service and have been running in production before the project, others are newly developed components and naturally lack maturity and are looking for sustainability options. This made the integration work for these services challenging and the Case Studies have opted for conservative integration strategies. These strategies ranged from merely piloting the components to assess their usability and only really integrate them at a later point in time to implementing alternative strategies for when the components are not available or functioning as expected and therefore not stopping the end-user workflow. The importance of sustainability cannot be stressed enough, and it is also felt that it is essential to ensure maximum uptake of the components themselves.

One Case Study has integrated with the Compliance Assessment Toolkit where it proved to be a useful tool to identify gaps in the Case Study service definitions and documentation. These gaps could then be addressed which resulted in a direct improvement for the Case Study. During this process of evaluating the service with the CAT tool, the input form was not considered as intuitive as possible. Test interaction with the CAT team was needed before being able to continue with the assessment. Providing clearer instructions in the form and on how to test the sampling and resolution of the DOIs specifically are the main recommendations for this service.

The Research Discovery Graph is used in all Case Studies and is considered useful to improve data discoverability by supporting validation of metadata before importing, a user friendly and clear user interface, allowing exploration of the data based on key metrics and it is integrated with the RAiD service. The natural language search is showing considerable potential, especially for users outside the community, but has some usability and stability issues which need to be improved. The data ingestion process can be complex due to the differences in data sources and require interaction with the provider to synchronise these differences.

All five Case Studies have integrated with the PID Graph. The main benefit of this service to the Case Studies is to give insight into the relations between objects, such as other research or projects. The integration with RAiD enhances this function even further. The available APIs offer useful functionalities allowing e.g. the harvesting of zBMATH entities and offering support for reverse PID lookups for DOIs. The main recommendations from the Case Studies include improving the support for the recently implemented related identifier and to make sure that this also allows to represent the relation between RAiDs to map complex project networks with a variety of sub-projects. Also a dedicated service to validate metadata before ingestion into the PIDGraph, similar to what is offered for the RDGraph, would be useful.

The PID Meta Resolver, used in two Case Studies, meets our expectations. It allows for the resolution of a variety of PID systems, which for simple resolutions is not so much affected by a lack of harmonization of profiles and schemas. Adding the community specific zBMATH and swMATH identifiers was a smooth process. To improve the service even further, it is suggested that the option to specify which provider to use for a lookup request, instead of using all the providers, be implemented.

Used by all Case Studies, the Metadata Schema Crosswalk Registry is a very exciting and promising service that, at its core, has delivered what it promised. The registry allows for the management of schemas, crosswalks and associated files. This is a service developed from scratch and thus had some stability and usability issues, but these have, as expected, matured and stabilised towards the end of the project. Stability

and sustainability of the service is expected to be further improved. The crosswalk functionality has directly improved several Case Studies by e.g. speeding up the process to create communities and share research data in B2SHARE, allows for the automation of type conversion and improved machine aided analysis for the Climate community. Our recommendations for this component include support for relations between formats, such as a relation between CodeMeta for swMATH and CodeMeta. Given the complexity of the service documentation, hints and error messages in the API and UI can be further improved.

The Data Type Registry is used by four Case Studies. One Case Study originally intended to use the DTR but concluded that the MSCR was offering sufficient functionalities. The service easily fulfils the type requirements for the Case Studies making them able to use machine actionable typing. The registry also supports the definition of more complex types. Our main recommendation is to look into strategies to lower the risk of type duplication. In the current registry it is really easy to create new types but it is considered more difficult to find and re-use existing types. This results in duplicated types amplifying the issue because it is more difficult to find a relevant type if there are already many duplicates.

Three Case Studies are making use of the RAiD service. The administration of project related information is seen as a big challenge where RAiD can offer an innovative solution. The underlying metadata model is flexible enough to accommodate different scenarios and the tight integration with PIDs and DOIs allow for automatic integration into the PIDGraph and RDGraph. This is also a fairly new service and thus has some areas where it can be further improved. Support for data without a PID should be improved since there are many contexts in which not all data has PIDs assigned but still should be linked into a RAiD. The related identifier support is considered very useful but the current limit of about 300 related identifiers per RAiD is too low for some of the Case Studies. The management of user rights is also recommended to be enhanced. In a larger context, it is really required that parts of the management responsibility be delegated to other institutions, individuals, or even third parties. Despite the technical recommendations, this component also requires a higher emphasis into the business model and governance model of RAiD, both for SURF as the European registration agency, but in a national context as well.

The Research Software APIs and Connectors are used by one Case Study to archive some of their software. The archival process was smooth and the API was easy to use. The biggest hurdle was the validation of the CodeMeta integration. This process did require a lot of back and forth and having a dedicated CodeMeta validation service would have made this process a lot easier.

One Case Study expressed interest in The Software Heritage Mirror. After conducting a small study, as explained in section 2.4.2, into the usability it was concluded that better support is required for research specific PIDs, namely ORCIDs and RORs, to be of potential interest for national and/or organizational services. Because of this, this component has not been integrated into any Case Study, and therefore, no experiences or recommendations are available to be shared.

4 References

No	Description/Link
R1	Zamani, T., & Koumantaros, K. (2024). D1.4 FAIRCORE4EOOSC Cross-integration Beta Release Report. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12623667
R2	Main website for the Infrastructure for the European Network for Earth System Modelling project, https://is.enes.org/index.html
R3	Climate4Impact website, https://www.climate4impact.eu
R4	The Copernicus Climate Change Service website, https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu
R5	The Handle.Net Registry website, https://handle.net/
R6	The Coupled Model Intercomparison Project website, https://wcrp-cmip.org/
R7	Kruess, B. (2025). Climate Change case study: RAiD, DTR and MSCR definitions (V1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019497
R8	The Earth System Grid Federation, https://esgf.llnl.gov/mission.html
R9	Kruess, B. (2025). Climate Change case study: RAiD, DTR and MSCR definitions (V1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019497
R10	The CF metadata conventions website, https://cfconventions.org/
R11	Kruess, B. (2025). Climate Change case study: RAiD, DTR and MSCR definitions (V1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019497
R12	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019497 , example available in annex 5.1: DTR type: application/netcdf definition
R13	Kruess, B. (2025). Climate Change case study: RAiD, DTR and MSCR definitions (V1.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15019497
R14	The SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs website, https://stacspect.org/en
R15	The Fair Digital Objects Forum website, https://fairdo.org/
R16	Kulüke, M., Peters-von Gehlen, K., & Anders, I. (2025). Deliverable D3.5 - Report on domain-specific FDO standard. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14752859
R17	The Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe website, https://www.esiwace.eu/
R18	Widmann, H., Anders, I., Kulüke, M., Kruess, B., & Peters-von Gehlen, K. (2025, März 11). Interoperability between Data Spaces in Climate Science: Using DTR to specify STAC Catalogs defined as FDO. FAIRfest: Celebrating advancements of FAIR solutions in EOOSC, Den Haag, The Netherlands, 20–21 February 2025. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15006719
R19	The Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure website, https://www.clarin.eu/
R20	The Switchboard PUBLIC API Specification, https://github.com/clarin-eric/switchboard-doc/blob/master/documentation/PublicAPI.md
R21	Elbers, W. (2025). FAIRCORE4EOOSC SSH Case Study DTR Types [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15000074
R22	The Text Encoding Initiative website, https://tei-c.org/
R23	Elbers, W. (2025). FAIRCORE4EOOSC SSH Case Study DTR Types [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15000074 . Example available in annex 5.2: DTR type: application/tei+xml definition
R24	The Switchboard Tool Inventory, https://switchboard.clarin.eu/tools
R25	Research.fi website, https://research.fi/
R26	Developing Research Information Hub in Finland, a view from the Ministry https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.044
R27	About Publinova, https://publinova.nl/en/about

R28	Common European Research Information Format https://eurocris.org/services
R29	The CERIF Core specification, https://github.com/EuroCRIS/CERIF-Core
R30	OpenAIRE Guidelines for CRIS Managers, https://openaire-guidelines-for-cris-managers.readthedocs.io/en/v1.2.0/
R31	Piloting the use of PIDGraph data in Research.fi, Procedia Computer Science, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.069
R32	Piloting the use of RAiD in Research.fi, Procedia Computer Science https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.068
R33	Research projects in the research.fi service, https://research.fi/en/results/projects
R34	Implementing interoperability - Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry approach to FAIR metadata mappings, Proceedings of EUNIS 2024 annual congress in Athens, vol 105, pages 58-68, https://doi.org/10.29007/khls
R35	CRIS systems integration as a case study for the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry, Procedia Computer Science https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.070
R36	Advice for Metadata standards and agreements in applied science (in Dutch). https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12701230
R37	Edustandaard Agreements for Bibliographic Metadata using MODS (in Dutch) Metadata Object Description Scheme (MODS) - Metadata Object Description Scheme versie 1.3 - Edustandaard

Appendix I. DTR type: application/netcdf definition

Example of the “application/netcdf” DTR ExtendedMimeType type definition used in the Climate Case Study.

```
{
  "Identifier": "21.T11969/eb2d9d6700f3d1697c42",
  "name": "application/netcdf",
  "description": "Network Common Data Format (netCDF)",
  "provenance": {
    "contributors": [
      {
        "Name": "Beate Kruess"
      }
    ],
    "creationDate": "2024-10-24T14:40:55.407Z",
    "lastModificationDate": "2024-10-24T15:00:37.144Z"
  },
  "Taxonomies": [
    "21.T11969/d2005cc206ccbdfdef2b"
  ],
  "typeName": "application",
  "subTypeName": "netcdf",
  "references": [
    {
      "referenceName": "Unidata->NetCDF",
      "referenceURL": "https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/"
    }
  ],
  "encodingConsiderations": [
    "binary"
  ],
  "additionalInformation": {
    "magicNumbers": [
      "C', 'D', 'F', '\\001' at start of file - classic format (CDF-1)",
      "C', 'D', 'F', '\\002' at start of file - 64-bit offset format (CDF-2)",
      "C', 'D', 'F', '\\005' at start of file - 64-bit data format (CDF-5)",
      "\\211', 'H', 'D', 'F', '\\r', '\\n', '\\032', '\\n' at start of file - netCDF-4/HDF5"
    ],
    "fileExtensions": [
      ".nc",
      ".cdf",
      ".nc3",
      ".nc4"
    ]
  },
  "intendedUsage": "COMMON",
  "generalComment": "created as test MIME type, there is an initiative from UNIDATA to register this type in IANA: https://www.iana.org/assignments/provisional-standard-media-types/provisional-standard-media-types.xhtml"
}
```

Appendix II. DTR type: application/tei+xml definition

Example of the “application/tei+xml” DTR ExtendedMimeType type definition used in the SSH Case study.

```
{
  "Identifier": "21.T11969/710b1a3647d431e205e0",
  "name": "application/tei+xml",
  "description": "Text Encoding and Interchange (TEI) is an international and interdisciplinary standard that is widely used by libraries, museums, publishers, and individual scholars to represent all kinds of textual material for online research and teaching",
  "provenance": {
    "contributors": [{
      "Name": "Willem Elbers"
    }],
    "creationDate": "2024-11-25T10:34:29.283Z",
    "lastModificationDate": "2025-01-20T14:35:31.819Z"
  },
  "Aliases": [
    "application/tei+xml"
  ],
  "Taxonomies": [
    "21.T11969/fe61e4792b37f2bbb26e"
  ],
  "typeName": "application",
  "subTypeName": "tei+xml",
  "references": [{
    "referenceName": "RFC",
    "referenceURL": "https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc6129"
  }, {
    "referenceName": "SCHEMA",
    "referenceURL": "https://tei-c.org/release/xml/tei/custom/schema/xsd/tei_lite_xml.xsd"
  }, {
    "referenceName": "CROSSWALK",
    "referenceURL": "https://mscr-test.2.rahtiapp.fi/datamodel-api/v2/crosswalk/21.T13999/EOSC-202501000349738"
  }
]
```

}}